

POLY CYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME - AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVEUpadhyay Bhavna^{1*}, Dr. Shivani Gupta Borele²

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ABSTRACT

There is immense role of Ayurveda in endocrine disorders. Endocrine system consists of hormones, these hormones regulate the body.

There is no direct reference of endocrine system in Ayurveda, but we can co-orelate the symptoms caused in endocrine disorders according to Ayurveda.

PCOS is caused due to hormonal imbalance in modern science and ayurved treats pcos as full body disease and manages it accordingly. There is bright future in treating endocrine disorders according to Ayurveda. Ayurveda is an integrative regimen that balances body, mind, emotions, and consciousness; improves health by creating a deep shift which creates confidence and increases faith which further supports a higher level of overall healing. Without mentioning anything

specific about hormones of the endocrine system, Ayurveda Serves as the best way in healing disorders associated with it. It treats pcos harmlessly and with no side effects, the effectiveness of ayurvedic treatment in healing pcos restores our faith in role of ayurved in endocrine disorders.

KEYWORDS: PCOS, Endocrine disorder, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME (PCOS) is a multifactorial and polygenic condition. PCOS is the most common endocrine disorder of reproductive aged woman and

affects approx 4 to 12%. Although symptoms of androgen excess vary between ethnicity, PCOS appears to equally affect all races and nationalities.

It affects about 10% of women in reproductive age. The worldwide prevalence of pcos ranges from 2.2 to 26%. According to national health portal of india. The prevalence rate of PCOS in mumbai was noted to be 22.5%.

- Diagnosis is based upon the presence of any two of the following criteria of ASRM/ESHRE.

- 1) Oligo and /or anovulation,
- 2) hyperandrogenism clinical or biochemical,
- 3) Polycystic ovaries as per obesity is very common finding in PCOS parients.

Polycystic overies were only recognised as a typical manifestation of PCOS during the 2003 Rotterdam Conference.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Authentic classical texts of ayurved, classical manuals and textbooks of mental disorders, published articles from Ayush Portal, PubMed, and other peer reviewed journals.

RESULTS

The detailed analysis of PCOS is discussed here, the ayurvedic representation of PCOS is also elaborated here.

- PCOS-afflicted women are more likely to develop a number of illnesses, such as endometrial cancer, depression, obesity, metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, and impaired glucose tolerance.
- The diagnostic symptoms of PCOS are anovulation, hirsutism, sonographic findings suggestive of cyst in ovary.
- PCOS is a highly complex endocrine disorder.
- It is a leading cause of infertility, menstrual disturbance and is associated with obesity, hirsutism and chronic anovulation.

- PCOS can't be correlated with a single entity in Ayurveda but has some resemblance with pushpaghnijatiharini. Others are shandi yoni vyapad, bandhya of Charak, bandhya yoni vyapad of Sushruta, vikutajatiharini of Kashyap.
- Obesity is the main cause and symptom which can be prevented by following dincharya and ritucharya and can be reduce by pathyaaahar, vihar, aushadh and restriction of apathyaaaharvihar.
- PCOS - Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome is a multifactorial disease involving endocrine and metabolic aspects. It is also known as Stein - Leventhal Syndrome. Prevalence rate of PCOS is 4% - 20% globally effecting women of reproductive age group. Menstrual abnormalities such as amenorrhoea, oligomenorrhoea, menorrhagia, Anovulation, infertility, obesity, excessive hair growth, acne are the characteristics of PCOS.
- PCOS is mainly as a result of Hyperandrogenism that is excess formation of androgens and insulinresistance which leads to deviation in HP Oaxiscausing hormonal imbalance and menstrual irregularities.
- Due to excess production of androgens, follicular growth is arrested forming multiple cyst making ovaries bulky and lazy. It is a complex disorder debiliting self-esteem of a woman by changes in physical appearance as well as effecting mental stability. Changing life style, dietary habits, stress and impatience has led to negative impact on health causing numerous disorders.
- PCOS is a classic example of lifestyle disorder which needs to inculcate *Ayurvedic* modifications. *Ayurveda* is a blessing as the guiding principle is to cure both physical and mental health and so there is an immense need to heal up the health loss and prevent further deterioration.
- In India 9.3% of women are diagnosed with PCOS. High androgen levels, irregular menstruation and tiny cysts on one or both ovaries are the hall marks of PCOS which is a complex condition. Changes in lifestyle, unhealthy eating patterns, inactivity, and stressful life events are contributing causes to PCOS. Reproductive health of a woman is disturbed due to PCOS.
- PCOS causes weight gain, irregular menstruation, and physical appearance changes that

exacerbate psychological issues. Therefore, early identification is crucial to preventing more serious consequences that could result in metabolic dysfunction.

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- PCOS causes weight gain, irregular menstruation, and physical appearance changes that exacerbate psychological issues. Therefore, early identification is crucial to preventing more serious consequences that could result in metabolic dysfunction. With Ayurvedic perspective PCOS resembles few diseases which are various yonivyapad, granthi, apache, apakvavran, sthauya which are described here.
- *Tryavartayoni* and the illnesses associated with it are discussed in the classics of *Ayurveda* under the term *Yonivyapad*.^[1]
- The phrase *Yonivyapad* is used to explain that what disturbs the normalcy.
- **Various other conditions causing Amenorrhoea or scanty menses resembling to Artavkshay are as follows.**
 - *ArajaskaYonivyapat*^[14]
 - *ShandhiYonivyapat*^[15]
 - *VandhyaYoni*^[16]
 - *KshinaArtavadushti*^[17]

- *Vataja Artavadushti*^[18]
- *Nashtartav/Anartav*^[19]

1. *Arajaska Yonivyapad* described by *Acharya Charakis* called *Lohitakshaya* or *Lohitaksharaby* others. It is a condition marked by amenorrhoea of a secondary variety. It is accompanied with burning syndrome, emaciation and general pallor.

- योनिगर्भाशयस्थं चेत् पित्तं सन्दूषयेदसृक्
- साऽरजस्का मता कार्श्यवैवर्ण्यजननी भृशम्॥१७॥^[11]

2. *Shandhi Yoni* is a condition characterized by Amenorrhoea and underdeveloped breast-tissue. This is said to be a congenital deformity. This sort of uterine amenorrhoea is derived from gross-under development of uterus

- बीजदोषातुगभास्मिमारुतोपहताशया।
- नृद्वेषणयस्तनीचैषिण्डीस्यादनुपक्रमा॥(च.नच.३०/२)^[12]

3. *Vandhya Yoni* is characterised by amenorrhoea, where it is said the menses are destroyed.

4. *Kshina Artavadushti* is caused by *Vata and Pitta dosha*. In this condition menstruation is delayed, menstrual blood is scanty & associated with pain in vagina.

5. *Vataja Artavadushti* is due to vitiation of *vayu*. Menstruation is accompanied with dull aching (*Tod*) or excruciating (*bheda*) pain. Flow is scanty and blackish in colour.

6. *Nashtartava* is described by *Acharya Sushrut* and *Anartav* is explained by *Acharya Vagbhat* which means absence of menses resembling with Amenorrhea. It is due to aggravation of *Kapha* and *Vata dosha* causing obstruction to *Artavvahastrotas*.

1. GRANTHI

The Doshas (*Vata, Pitta and Kapha*) contaminated the *mamsa* (muscles) and *asruk* (blood), *meda* (fat) and *siraa* (vein, blood vessel) causes an elevated swelling which is rounded and knotted (clotted). Such swelling will be called as *Granthi*. When the cyst (*granthi*) occurs specifically in *sira*, it will be called *sira granthi*.^[20]

2. APACHE

Some of the swellings undergo suppuration, some more burst open and discharge their contents, some get destroyed or disappear, and some new ones appear. This process continues for a long time. Experts call such conditions as Apaci. This condition is curable. On the other hand, apaci associated with complications like running from the nose, pain in the flanks, cough, fever and vomiting will become incurable.^[21]

3. STHAULYA

A person who due to excessive accumulation of muscles and fat in the body presents with sagging butts, abdomen and breasts, the muscles and fat tissue are nourished and formed normally (they are abnormally deposited) and the energy levels also are not normal (below normal) is called atisthula or obese.

4. VIDRADHI

The aggravated doshas vitiate the skin, blood, muscle and fat tissues.

Following this, the doshas get localized in the bone tissue and produce troublesome swelling. This swelling slowly bulges up, gets deep rooted, is round or wide in shape and is painful. This swelling is called Vidradhi.^[22]

5. APAKVAVRAN

Symptoms – Below mentioned are the symptoms of unripe swellings –

- mild increase in temperature
- color of the swelling will be same as the color of the surrounding skin
- cold in touch,
- immovable,
- associated with mild pain
- there will be slight swelling.^[23]

RASAVAHASTROTAS DUSHTI OCCURS IN PCOS

श्लेष्माऽग्निसदनप्रसेकालस्यगौरवम्

श्वैत्यशैत्यश्लथाङ्गत्वं श्वासकासातिनिद्रताः।

Artava is the *Updhatu* of *Rasadhatu*. *Vagbhata* signifies that the *kshaya* of *upadhatu* is dependent on the *kshaya* of *purvadhātu*. As *Artava* is *upadhatu* of *Rasa*, *Sushruta* has said

that *Rasakshaya* is also one of the causes of its *Kshay*. PCOS is a metabolic disorder disrupting the normal metabolism at cellular level which can be correlated with *agnimandya* leading to *Rasadhatudushti* and hence *upadhatuie. Artavadushti*.

DISCUSSION

This chronic and heterogeneous disorder manifests itself as menstrual dysfunction, infertility, hirsutism, acne, and obesity. It describes a condition where at least one ovary has an ovarian volume greater than 10 mL and at least one ovary has an estimated ten small cysts, with diameters ranging from 2 to 9 mm, develop. It is usually only diagnosed when complications develop that significantly reduce a patient's quality of life (e.g., hair loss, alopecia, acne, and infertility-related problems). According to a systematic screening of women using the National Institutes of Health (NIH) diagnostic standards, 4–10% of reproductive-age women are predicted to have PCOS worldwide.^[13]

There is no direct reference of PCOS in Ayurveda In Ayurveda we do diagnosis with the principles of Dosh, Dushya, Srotus and Srotodushtiprakar and there is no need of hormonal evaluation for this sake. In Ayurveda with above said principles, diagnosis which is similar to PCOS can be granthi, apachi, sthaulya, vidradhi, apakvavran and Rasavaha strotas dushti.

Updhatu of Rasavahstrotas is stanya and artava. Hence, the medicine which act of artava also acts on stanya and hence HRT may cause carcinoma of breast, breast tenderness and heaviness. The treatment of hrt works on imbalance due to cyst, hence the treatment causes functional changes in female but no anatomical changes noted with respect to cyst as an aspiring student of Ayurveda, I have seen many cases of PCOS being treated successfully the result shows changes in ovary and the menstrual cycle resumed is functionally and anatomically natural. In Ayurveda resumption of menstrual cycle is not the treatment, instead the patient is treated wholly.

PCOS accompanying obesity, hairfall, hirsutism and infertility is treated as whole according to Ayurveda. The role of Ayurveda in endocrine disorder is immense and the results are satisfying to a great degree PCOS is a complex ailment caused due to imbalance of hormones leading to ovarian malfunction. The cardinal sign of PCOS is amenorrhoea or oligo-hypomenorrhoea. These clinical characteristics are similar to those of Artavkshay because both disorders have delayed or absent Rajasrava (menstruation).

The need of the hour is to embrace Ayurveda and learn its concept fruitfully so that patient gets benefitted.

CONCLUSION

To treat a woman affected with PCOS need controlled and balanced diet and exercise for weight reduction along with medication, preventive measures are more important. So it will be more beneficial to follow mode of life as mentioned in Ayurveda and to use modern medicine, if needed, to get conceived.

REFERENCE

1. Dutta D.C. Text book of Gynaecology. 4th edition. Culcutta: New central book Agency LTD; 421. (431, 523, 549, 558).
2. Drjyotijain, management of nashtartavawrtpcos.
3. Dutta D.C. Text book of Gynaecology. 4th edition. Culcutta: New central book Agency LTD; 421. (431, 523, 549, 558).
4. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8448320/#pone.0255676.s007>.
5. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK534854/>
6. Sharma P.V. Charaka Samhita (English Translation) Chaukambha.
7. WHO GUIDELINES FOR RESEARCH.
8. MAYOCLINIC.
9. http://hercules.0414.fi/isbn9514264266/html_x891.html. Endocrine and Metabolic changes in women with Polycystic ovary and with polycystic ovary syndrome. Ritta Koivynan. Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology; University of Ohio, 2001.
10. <http://www.whatreallywork.co.uk/start/ayurvedizone.asp> article 1D=1345.
11. Sharma P. V. Charak Samhita nidansthan 30/17.
12. Sharma P. V. Charak Samhita nidansthan 30/2.
13. NATIONAL LIBRARY OF MEDICINE.
14. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charaka-samhita, chaukhamba sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi, Chikitsasthaan adhaya 30: edition-2009.
15. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charaka-samhita, chaukhamba sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi, Chikitsasthaan adhaya 30: edition-2009.
16. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba uttarsthaan 38.
17. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba uttarsthaan 38.
18. Ashtang sangrah sharirsthaan adhyaya 9.

19. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba sharirsthaan 2.
20. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba nidansthaan 13.
21. Madhav nidansthaan chapter 38.
22. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba nidansthaan
CHAPTER 9.
23. Dr. Anantram sharma, Sushruta Samhita, Pratham bhag, Chaukhamaba sutrasthaan
chapter 17.